

EDUCARE: A VIDEO PRODUCTION FOR TEACHERS IN RESPONSE TO EDUCATION 4.0 IN CAVITE PROVINCE

PRIMO P VILLANUEVA JR.¹, BETHEL NARCISO ZURBANO²

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4667-7773>¹

primovillanuevajr@gmail.com¹, hernandez.bethel@gma.uphsl.edu.ph²

College of Education Univeristy of Perpetual Help System GMA GMA Cavite, Philippines¹,
College of Arts and Sciences, and Education Univeristy of Perpetual Help System GMA GMA
Cavite, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

This study was influenced by key notes speeches of known educators. As implied, teachers have to prepare in the advent of education 4.0. Learners are seen to be gadget dependent. They are acquiring informal educations in many forms through smartphones via net. The social media has shown its power to influence our young ones and even professionals. The general problem is focused on the attitude, skills and knowledge of teachers in digital technology towards education 4.0 through adaptation on lecture videos. This study used KSA model of business, Bloom's domain of learning and structured functional theory. This has conceptualized the 4C-shells of mind, structured functional model of sub-educational elements and Input-Process-Output model. The respondents came from different legislative district of province of Cavite conducted using random sampling methods via google forms. Descriptive and inferential statistics such as z-test, ANOVA, HSD Tukey's test, and Levene's test of homogeneity were used including the PBR Principle and 8 scaled balanced value and agreement evaluation. The study found out that the teachers, in terms of sex, age, type of serviced school and even instructional level handled, have a very high positive attitudes on adaptation of digital technology specifically on video production. Only, the skills are affected by lack of knowledge on the advancements of technology. Also, most of the teachers are already giving students different activities that use digital technology. It has concluded that teachers need more of workshops or e- workshops where they will be doing the lecture video. This will enhance their critical and creative thinking as well as communication skills and character. Also, a class studio must be provided in order for them including education students to showcase their lecture video production skills and abilities empowering the concept of teaching as an art and science.

Keywords: Education 4.0 in GMA Cavite, EDUCARE, Video Production for Teachers, Lecture Video, Technology